

Nowadays, one of the biggest challenges is to extract relevant information from large amount of data. To understand indications and map their interrelationships in the health, pharma, FMCG, marketing and IT industry complex algorithms are needed to identify individual customer groups, analyze area progressions, identify endpoints that occur, and create predictions.

What is our solution good for?

The analytical solution based on machine learning developed by Spicy Analytics Ltd. helps professionals in the following areas:

- Based on descriptive future events can be predicted
- Homogeneous product or consumer segments can be identified
- By recognizing the differences, communication and/or recommendation can be changed and strengthened.
- The most important stages of a process become recognizable.

Case Studies:

- Segmentation of patients diagnosed with heart failure before and after diagnosis, and finding typical pathways.
- Segmentation of patients diagnosed with renal failure before and after diagnosis and finding typical patient paths.
- Determination of surgical risk due to nutritional status.
- Determining the parameters for successful inclusion in Clinical Research.
- Segmentation of PCOS patients (polycystic ovarian syndrome) before and after diagnosis and finding pathways.
- Segmentation of patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome before and after diagnosis and finding typical pathways.

For further inquiries, please, contact us at the contact details below!

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